

Impact of Graduate Studies Degree on Public Administration Graduates' Professional Success

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Abstract

This study focused on examining the impact graduate studies on the Public Administration graduates from Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Valenzuela (PLV). The research aims to determine whether earning a graduate studies degree contributes to the professional success of the graduates. A descriptive research design was used in the study, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches. Survey questionnaires were administered to 33 graduates who completed their bachelor's degrees between 2006 to 2016. While interviews were conducted with selected key informants, 5 responses were gathered that supported the survey results. The findings showed that most graduates who pursued graduate studies were employed in the public sector, were skilled and experienced, held permanent positions, and believed that their advanced education contributed to their career advancement and leadership development. Despite these benefits, graduates also reported challenges such as institutional barriers, problems with the qualifications standard and the patronage systems.

Keywords: Career Advancement; Employment Status; Graduate Studies; Professional Success; Public Administration

INTRODUCTION

Public administration plays a vital role in implementing government policies and improving public services. As workplace demands continue to evolve, pursuing graduate studies in public administration has become important for developing advanced knowledge, leadership skills, and professional competence. International studies show that graduates with advanced degrees in public administration often experience better employment opportunities, career advancement, and leadership roles. In the Philippines, many professionals pursue graduate education to improve their

qualifications, increase salary opportunities, and achieve career growth despite challenges such as limited promotion opportunities and institutional barriers.

Despite the growing number of graduate degree holders, there is limited evidence on how graduate studies specifically influence the professional success of Public Administration graduates in the Philippine context. This study aims to assess the impact of graduate education on career advancement, employment status, leadership opportunities, salary growth, and job performance among Public Administration graduates. It also seeks to

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determine how advanced education contributes to strengthening public service and governance. The findings of this study may provide valuable insights for students, educational institutions, employers, and policymakers in improving professional development and public sector performance.

Ultimately, this study aims to examine the current status of PLV Public Administration graduates, particularly in terms of their level of satisfaction with their professional success, the challenges they encounter, and the recommendations they can offer to improve career outcomes and better connect education with real-world demands. The following are the research questions that this study seeks to address:

1. What is the current status of Public Administration graduates in terms of:
 - 1.1 Education
 - 1.2 Year Graduate
 - 1.3 Job Title
 - 1.4 Employment Status
 - 1.5 Employment Sector
2. How do graduates assess the importance of a graduate studies degree in achieving professional success?
3. What opportunities are offered to Public Administration graduates with graduate studies degrees on their employment?
4. What challenges do Public Administration graduates encounter despite completing their graduate studies?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what program plan will be developed to enhance Public Administration to encourage graduates to enroll in the graduate program to achieve professional success?

Despite the growing number of professionals pursuing graduate studies in Public Administration, there is still limited research in the Philippine context examining how advanced degrees influence the professional success of graduates. Existing studies mainly focus on general employability and career development, with little attention given to the specific effects of graduate education on career advancement, leadership opportunities, employment status, salary growth, and job performance among Public Administration graduates. This gap highlights the need for further research to determine how graduate studies contribute to professional growth and public service effectiveness.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-method approach using a convergent parallel design to examine the influence of graduate studies on the professional success of Public Administration graduates. Quantitative and qualitative data were collected simultaneously, analyzed separately, and integrated to provide a comprehensive understanding of the study. The quantitative component focused on graduates' educational attainment, employment status, job position, and perceptions regarding the contribution of graduate studies to career success.

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Meanwhile, the qualitative component explored the personal experiences, opportunities, and challenges encountered by graduates through interviews and open-ended responses.

The study was conducted at Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Valenzuela, particularly among Bachelor of Science in Public Administration (BSPA) graduates from 2006 to 2016 who had pursued graduate studies. Non-probability snowball sampling was utilized to identify participants. The respondents consisted of at least 30 survey participants and 5–10 interviewees from various employment sectors, including government, private institutions, and non-government organizations.

Data were gathered through structured survey questionnaires, interviews, and document analysis of alumni and school records. Surveys collected quantitative information regarding employment status, promotions, salary changes, and professional development, while interviews provided deeper insights into graduates' experiences and perceptions of graduate education.

The study utilized descriptive quantitative and qualitative analysis, thematic analysis, content analysis, document analysis, and Likert scale analysis. Frequency, percentage distribution, and weighted mean were used to interpret quantitative data, while qualitative responses were analyzed to identify recurring themes and patterns related to career advancement and professional success.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the study. Participants were informed about the purpose of the research and voluntarily provided informed consent. Confidentiality, anonymity, data privacy, and secure handling of records were ensured in accordance with ethical research standards and the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The current status of Public Administration graduates in terms of: Education, Year Graduated, Employment Category, Employment Status and Employment Sector

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents' Educational Attainment by Graduate Degree Level

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Doctoral Degree	2	6.1%
Master's Degree	31	93.9
Total	33	100%

Most respondents with graduate degrees in public administration hold master's degrees, accounting for 93.9%, while only 6.1% have doctoral degrees,

indicating a predominance of master's degree holders among the participants.

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Table 2

Distribution of Respondents by the Year Graduated

Year	Frequency	Percentage
2016	2	6.06%
2015	2	6.06%
2014	2	6.06%
2013	7	21.21%
2012	6	18.18%
2011	3	9.09%
2010	2	6.06%
2009	2	6.06%
2008	2	6.06%
2007	3	9.09%
2006	2	6.06%
Total	33	100%

Table 2 shows the distribution of public administration graduates with graduate studies degrees from 2006 to 2016, totaling 33 graduates. The peak occurred in 2013 with 7 graduates (21.21%), followed by 2012 with 6 (18.18%), and 2007 and 2011 with 3 each (9.09%). Several years, including 2006, 2008-2010, 2014-2016, each had 2 graduates (6.06%). The data indicates a relatively stable number of graduates with notable increases in 2012 and 2013, possibly influenced by various factors affecting enrollment and completion,

providing an overview of changes over the eleven-year period.

Table 3

Distribution of Job Roles by Employment Categories

Job Roles	Frequency	Percentage
Academic/Education	8	23.53%
Administrative/Office Support	14	41.2%
Management	5	14.71%
Public Service/Government	6	17.65%
Finance	1	2.94%
Total	34	100%

The distribution of Public Administration alumni with graduate degrees is categorized by their current job roles, with some alumni counted in multiple categories due to holding multiple positions. The most common category is Administrative/Office Support, with 14 roles, highlighting that many alumni work in administrative and operational positions, demonstrating the relevance of their training to organizational management and governance tasks in various sectors.

Table 4

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Current Employment Status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Co - Terminuos	1	3.0%
Casual	3	9.1%
Non - Permanent	3	9.1%
Permanent	26	78.8%
Total	33	100%

Most alumni (78.8%) hold permanent jobs in the public or private sectors, indicating successful graduate employment and skill development. A minority (9.1% each) are in casual or non-permanent roles, with only 3.0% in co-terminus positions. Overall, permanent employment is the most common outcome, suggesting favorable employment conditions.

Table 5

Employment Sector

Employment Sector	Frequency	Percentage
Private	7	21.21%
Public	26	78.79%
Total	33	100%

Most alumni prefer government employment, with 78.79% working in

public offices, citing stability and benefits. Only 21.21% are in the private sector, and none are in non-profit or NGO sectors, indicating limited interest or opportunities outside government. Overall, government jobs are the most favored and accessible career choice for alumni.

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2. Assessment of the importance of the graduate studies degree in achieving professional success.

Table 6

Education and Graduate Studies

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. My educational background has provided me with the skills necessary for my professional career.	3.70	Strongly Agree
2. Earning a graduate degree in Public Administration gives graduates an advantage in the job market.	3.64	Strongly Agree
3. Participation in further training (seminars, workshops, or certifications) has strengthened my career development.	3.70	Strongly Agree
4. The courses I completed in graduate school are relevant to the responsibilities of my current job.	3.58	Strongly Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	3.65	Strongly Agree

Respondents strongly agree that their educational background has provided them with essential professional skills, supported by a high weighted mean of 3.70 and interview insights emphasizing the practical nature of graduate studies. They also agree that participation in seminars and training enhances career development, with the same weighted mean. Employers tend to favor applicants with graduate degrees, as reflected in key informants' statements and supported by literature indicating higher chances of promotion, salary increases, and leadership roles for graduates.

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Table 7
Career Experience

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. My current job position reflects the competencies I gained through my graduate studies.	3.55	Strongly Agree
2. Having a graduate degree has helped me attain a higher position at work.	3.39	Strongly Agree
3. My graduate education in Public Administration has prepared me for leadership or managerial roles.	3.64	Strongly Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	3.52	Strongly Agree

Table 7 shows that respondents strongly agree their graduate studies have positively impacted their careers by increasing knowledge and skills. The data indicates that years since graduation significantly contribute to career resilience, integrity, and transparency, aligning with Magbanua (2025), which found postgraduate education enhances workplace adaptability in government. Key Informant 2 highlighted that graduate education enhances relevant expertise, emphasizing the importance of experience directly related to current work, supporting Julieta et al. (2020), who noted that graduate programs develop enduring

knowledge and skills that help stabilize professional and personal priorities.

Table 8
Job Title

Table 8 indicates that respondents strongly agree their current jobs reflect the competencies gained from their graduate studies, with a mean of 3.55. Key Informant 4 described how graduate knowledge

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Grand Weighted Mean	3.65	Strongly Agree

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enabled them to handle complex tasks and higher positions in the Philippine National Police, involving exposure to various methodologies such as performance systems, quality management, ISO certification, and anti-criminality plans. Recent studies support that graduate education enhances professional skills, critical thinking, and adaptability in complex roles, particularly in the public sector, demonstrating that advanced education prepares graduates for challenging responsibilities and higher-level functions.

Table 9
Employment Sector

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. My graduate degree has helped me secure employment in my preferred sector (public, private, or non-government).	3.52	Strongly Agree
2. Employers in my sector recognize the relevance of a graduate degree in Public Administration.	3.39	Strongly Agree
3. The nature of my work allows me to apply the concepts and practices learned in graduate school.	3.58	Strongly Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	3.49	Strongly Agree

Table 9 indicates that respondents strongly believe their graduate degrees positively influence their employment opportunities across public, private, and non-government sectors. The statement “My graduate degree has helped me secure employment in my preferred sector” scored a mean of 3.52, reflecting strong support for the program’s relevance to job placement. Key Informant 4 confirmed this, noting that their graduate studies in public policy and governance directly apply to their

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government work. This suggests that relevant training enhances graduates' job performance and employability, especially when their field of study aligns with employer needs. Recent research supports this, indicating that graduate education improves employment prospects and matches skills with suitable roles in public service (Reyes, 2022; Navarro & Cruz, 2023).

Table 10

Professional Success & Satisfaction

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The number of years since I graduated has influenced my career growth.	3.67	Strongly Agree
2. The knowledge and competencies I acquired during my studies continue to be useful in my current work.	3.73	Strongly Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	3.58	Strongly Agree

Alumni strongly agree that pursuing graduate studies is vital for career advancement and improves job prospects, with a high weighted mean of 3.70. Graduate education is viewed as crucial for enhancing employability and competitiveness. Supporting this, a key informant noted that college teachers are expected to have a Master's Degree to teach at the undergraduate level, which provides a competitive edge. Furthermore, research indicates that employers value postgraduate

degrees for the skills they confer, which are essential for accessing higher professional opportunities and positions, underscoring the importance of graduate education for career success.

Table 11

Weighted Mean

Themes	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Education and Graduate Studies	3.65	Strongly Agree
Career Experience	3.52	Strongly Agree
Job Title	3.58	Strongly Agree
Employment Sector	3.49	Strongly Agree
Professional Success & Satisfaction	3.58	Strongly Agree
Importance of Graduate Studies	3.64	Strongly Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	3.57	Strongly Agree

The overall weighted mean of 3.57, under the category Strongly Agree, shows that the alumni have a consistent, favorable perception of the necessity of graduate studies. These results indicate that the respondents as a whole strongly recognize the valuable contribution of graduate education to their career success, professional development, and skill

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enhancement. The high overall weighted mean reveals a shared belief that graduate studies play an important role in improving employability, leadership, readiness, and analytical competencies. In general, the findings affirm that graduate education is highly valued and regarded as significant for career growth and advancement.

3. The opportunities offered to Public Administration graduates with graduate studies degrees on their employment.

Graduate Education Enhances Employment Opportunities Across Sectors

The graduates of public administration with graduate studies degrees are offered wider employment opportunities across the public, private, and academic sectors, based on the interviewee responses. Key informants perceived that it will open new avenues to various positions and facilitate cross-sector mobility, enhancing graduates' competitiveness and improving access to opportunities that may otherwise be limited by pursuing advanced education and obtaining graduate studies degree.

Advanced Degrees Boost Employability and Hiring Preference

Based on the collective responses from the key informants, obtaining an advanced degree significantly strengthens and advances employability and hiring preference regardless of the organization, whether it is in government agencies, private institutions, or academic institutions, which prioritize applicants especially with higher academic

preparation. In recruitment, promotion, and hiring processes, graduate education is an essential factor, and it can enhance credibility and strengthen an employee's expertise.

Graduate Studies as an Important Key for Promotion and Career Advancement

The collective responses from the participants emphasized graduate studies as a key requirement for promotion, permanent employment, and career advancement. The alumni highlight that the absence of a graduate studies degree provides only limited opportunities. This indicates that having a graduate degree helps employees get promoted and secure stable jobs.

4. The challenges Public Administration graduates encountered despite completing their graduate studies

Patronage and Backer System as the Main Challenge that Limits the Full Benefits of Graduate Education

Earning a graduate studies degree strengthened the qualifications of the alumni. However, many participants shared the challenges such as favoritism, the backer system, and political influence that limits their practical benefits. These issues often prevent qualified graduates from fully applying their knowledge and skills, as employment and promotion decisions are sometimes based on personal connections rather than merit.

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Overqualification and Limited Opportunities Despite Graduate Education

Participants expressed that earning a graduate degree definitely strengthens their skills and knowledge, making them more prepared and uplifting their critical thinking in decision-making process. However, they also pointed out that having this qualification does not guarantee employment, it is not an assurance for being hired. Many employers, especially for entry-level roles, see graduate degree holders as “overqualified” and hesitate to hire them. This shows that while education is important, experience, job fit, and employer perception also play a significant role in career opportunities, sometimes outweighing formal qualifications.

Insufficient Experience Limits the Application of Graduate Learning

Some participants explained that entering graduate school too early limits understanding of how government work functions on the ground and to gain experience and develop as an employee. Without real work experience, it becomes harder to connect theories with the daily realities of public service. Graduate studies demand applying concepts to real systems, and that application is easier when a student has seen those systems firsthand. Because of this, practical experience becomes an important foundation before pursuing advanced education.

SOP 5: The program plan based on the findings of the study.

Program Title: The Professional Growth and Career Advancement Program for Public Administration Graduates

Rationale

This program aids to the growing demand for Public Administration graduates that are ethical and with high competencies who are able to continuously adapt to diverse and emerging challenges in governance and the growing responsibilities for the public sector. Regardless of the evident benefits of graduate studies, many graduates still face challenges such as limited access to continuing professional development, financial constraints, and the lack of structured career guidance, which hinder their professional growth and leadership advancement. This program addresses these gaps by providing continuing professional development opportunities, offering scholarships and incentives for graduate and doctoral studies, and giving career guidance and leadership training. It also includes an alumni tracking system to follow career progress and use the results to improve academic programs. In general, the program strengthens the institution’s role in preparing public administrators who are ready for work and able to contribute effectively to public service and good governance.

Most PLV Public Administration graduates pursued graduate studies, particularly the Master in Public

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Administration, to improve their qualifications and professional skills. Most respondents are permanently employed, mainly in government agencies, while others work in private institutions, NGOs, and academic settings. Many graduates currently hold supervisory, managerial, or executive positions, indicating that graduate education contributed to career growth and leadership opportunities.

Graduates strongly agreed that graduate studies improved their knowledge, competencies, analytical skills, and decision-making abilities relevant to their work. Interview responses showed that advanced education increased their confidence and preparedness in handling professional responsibilities. The findings also revealed that graduate studies, together with work experience, contributed to promotions and long-term professional development.

Graduate studies also provided opportunities for promotion, leadership roles, salary increases, and professional recognition. Many respondents shared that advanced education strengthened their qualifications for supervisory and managerial positions, especially in government institutions. The skills gained also improved their effectiveness in performing public service and organizational duties.

Despite these benefits, graduates still experienced challenges such as limited promotion opportunities, rigid organizational systems, and underutilization of acquired skills. Many

also struggled to balance work, family responsibilities, and graduate studies, resulting in stress and financial strain. However, these challenges were generally viewed as temporary sacrifices that contributed to long-term career benefits.

The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings shows that graduate studies positively influence professional success by enhancing job stability, leadership capacity, career advancement, and professional confidence. The results suggest that graduate education strengthens both the competencies and professional identity of graduates, particularly in public service roles.

CONCLUSION

The conclusions of this study are based on the analysis of the impact of graduate studies on the professional success of Public Administration graduates. By examining alumni experiences, employment status, and career development, the study identified key factors that influence career advancement as well as challenges in applying graduate-level education. Overall, the findings provide useful insights for graduates, higher education institutions, and government agencies in strengthening graduate programs and improving the utilization of highly educated public administration professionals.

The study concludes that for most Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Valenzuela BSPA graduates, graduate education has a significant influence on career

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advancement, with most respondents employed in government agencies and holding master's degrees rather than doctoral degrees. Based on interviews, graduate education enhances job mobility and leadership opportunities, although it does not always guarantee job security. Survey results further show that graduate studies provide a competitive advantage by improving knowledge, competence, and employability, making graduates more qualified for hiring and promotion even in competitive fields.

Findings also indicate that graduate education is an important factor in achieving career progression, particularly in government and academic sectors where it is often required or highly preferred for advanced positions. However, graduates also reported institutional challenges such as favoritism, patronage systems, and structural barriers that limit promotion opportunities despite higher qualifications. In addition, some respondents experienced mismatches between their academic preparation and actual job requirements, with employers often prioritizing experience and networks over formal education.

The study further reveals that the benefits of graduate education are not consistently recognized across organizations, as career outcomes are still influenced by multiple factors beyond academic credentials. While some non-graduate degree holders attain high positions, some graduates remain in stagnant roles, suggesting that graduate education alone does not determine

professional success. Therefore, career advancement should be understood as a combination of education, experience, and workplace opportunities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study entitled "Impact of Graduate Studies Degree on Public Administration Graduates' Professional Success," several recommendations are proposed to enhance the professional development of graduates, improve graduate programs, and strengthen public service outcomes. These are directed toward higher education institutions, students and alumni, government agencies, and future researchers.

1. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)

HEIs are encouraged to promote graduate education among Public Administration students and alumni through career orientations, information campaigns, and guidance activities. Graduate studies should be emphasized as a long-term investment that enhances leadership skills, competencies, and career opportunities. Institutions may also implement development programs such as Continuing Professional Development (CPD), scholarship and incentive programs, alumni tracking systems, and career development workshops to support lifelong learning and career advancement. In addition, expanding graduate offerings such as doctoral programs may further strengthen academic and professional growth in the field.

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2. Public Administration Students and Alumni

Students and alumni are encouraged to build and maintain strong professional networks through alumni associations, organizations, conferences, and inter-agency collaborations. They should also engage in continuous upskilling through seminars, training, and certification programs to remain competitive in a changing work environment. In addition, they are advised to practice proactive career planning, self-development, and adaptability to fully maximize the benefits of graduate education and achieve long-term career success.

3. Government and Policy-Making Bodies

Government agencies are encouraged to recognize graduate education in hiring, promotion, and career advancement systems to ensure merit-based professional growth. Policies such as study leave, scholarships, and training incentives may also be implemented to support public servants pursuing graduate studies. Furthermore, government institutions should ensure that highly educated professionals are properly utilized in leadership, policy-making, and program implementation roles to prevent underutilization of skills and reduce talent waste.

4. Future Researchers

Future researchers are encouraged to expand the scope of this study by including more recent graduates (Batch 2017–2023) and examining their long-term

career development, job satisfaction, and leadership progression. Further studies may also explore how graduate education influences career outcomes across different sectors and time periods. This will provide more updated and comprehensive insights into the role of graduate education in professional success.

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